

THE PROBLEM OF FANTASTIC MOTIVES FOR THE STORY OF
F.M.DOSTOEVSKIY "DREAM OF A FUNNY MAN "

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of the ideological content of the story of F.M. Dostoevsky « Son of a funny man ». It is proposed to interpret this text as a quintessence of philosophical searches in « Writer's Diary ».

Keywords: F.M.Dostoevskiy, "Dream of a funny man", special literature, M.M. Bakhtin, Fantastic imagery

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« The writer's diary » as a special literary genre was conceived by Dostoevsky very early, and its implementation was only beginning in 1873. In the newspaper-magazine « Citizen », published by Prince V.P. Meshchersky, Dostoevsky publishes his first experiments in a planned genre. But only in 1876 begins to publish « Writer's Diary » independently, until 1881, that is, until the end of his life.

The thematic range of issues « Writer's Diary » is wide. They contain comments on major political events, active literary controversy and feedback on literary novelties, memories of Belinsky, Chernyshevsky, Herzen and even works of art. This is the story « Mole », « Vlas », « Bobok ». Especially noteworthy is the work related to the genre of science fiction, this is « Dream of a funny person » / 1877g/.

« The dream of a funny person » belongs to a very special place in the work of Dostoevsky. Much has been said about this work by large literary scholars. The work was interpreted from different angles, but in most cases something significant was ignored: « The dream of a funny person » is a fantastic story. But behind this genre characteristic is a lot.

The story was published in the April book « Writer's Diary » for 1877. Its significance is largely determined by the topic, which is relentlessly tormenting the writer throughout his career. The dream of the harmonious future of mankind, the conviction that this dream will be realized over time, permeates all of Dostoevsky's work, being his leitmotif. With the same artistic power with which the writer depicts the triumph of evil on earth, he also speaks of the inevitability in the future of the affirmation of truth, justice, humanity. This result gives us the effect of the

counterpoint of the whole thinking of the writer, the stable duality of everything in his artistic world.

« The dream of a funny person » is a story about a person, his spiritual ordeals in a tense search for truth. And a strictly fantastic element in this work is its plot design.

Who is he, « funny person », on behalf of whom the story is being conducted? The story consists of five small chapters. The first two of them are – exposure chapters. The hero speaks in them as a person finished, his soul is so devastated that he still has « », which means that everything, what happens around and in the world does not care about him.

But what does « funny person » see in his dream? Here, for the first time in his work, Dostoevsky paints a picture of a harmonious society with sufficient details. Idyllic tones and paints prevail in these descriptions. They are in the image of nature, and the creatures of this amazing world, their lifestyle, customs and customs.

Nature here clearly contrasts with the dominant St. Petersburg landscapes of the writer, most often « the poor » for residents. And here, on this fantastic island – « The gentle emerald sea quietly splashed on the shore and slaughtered them with love, obvious, visible, almost conscious.

Tall, beautiful trees stood in all the luxury of their color, and countless leaflets greeted me with their quiet, affectionate noise ... Birds flown in the air for herds and, not afraid of me, they sat on my shoulders and hands, and joyfully beat me with their cute, trepidable wings ».

But the main thing, of course, is people / the author calls / happy land. They are beautiful, happy and kind in the image of the author. « Children of the sun, children of their sun, oh how beautiful they were! » « The funny man » was met with extraordinary joy. They showered the alien with affection and kisses. « These people, laughing joyfully, clashed to me and caressed me to themselves, and any of them wanted to reassure me ».

« A funny person » dwells on the characteristic of the mental state of the inhabitants of this wonderful world. It turned out that they « did not have the sciences », « they did not seek to know life, since their life was filled ... but their knowledge was deeper than that of our science ». The narrator realizes that these creatures, whom he calls people, have the opportunity to communicate with all living things in some mysterious ways, and most importantly – with space. Dostoevsky's fiction in « Snow » is largely fed by Christian biblical origins. People on this fantastic land live like in paradise.

The book by M.M. Bakhtin « problems of the poetics of Dostoevsky » contains an exhaustive analysis of the poetics of the plot and the genre features of this story.

M.M. Bakhtin found that on its theme « Son of a funny man » is an almost complete encyclopedia of leading themes of Dostoevsky. [1]

Thus, in the content of sleep « funny person » two aspects should be noted. The first – is not only an opportunity, but also the need to establish harmony in human relations. The second – the danger of the destruction of this beautiful world to those evil principles that are not exterminated in the souls of people.

Fantastic stories « The diary of the writer » Dostoevsky are, to a certain extent, the final in the artistic work of the writer. The fantastic imagery in the story « The Dream of a Funny Man », as in previous works of Dostoevsky, is closely related to the image of a concrete realistic one.

With an abundance of fantastic images and motives, the priority in the stories « The Diary of the Writer » is the real reality of Russian life with all its difficult problems and hopes for a better future. Fantastic imagery in the vast majority of cases here is assigned the role of a plot technique that helps the writer to reveal the essence of what is happening in the world and in the depths of the spirituality of man.

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[1] M.M. Bakhtin. Problems of the poetics of Dostoevsky ... S. 201.